

WORDS INDICATING SIGNS OF ACTION IN ANCIENT AND OLD TURKISH LANGUAGES

Alijonova Fotima Odiljon qizi

Namangan city school No. 37 teacher of native language and literature, master

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10617572>

Abstract: In this article, researches and scientific-theoretical views on words denoting action in ancient and old Turkic languages are analyzed.

Key words: ancient Turkic language, old Turkic language, ravish, word group, word structure, rigid invariant form, o'tru, kiswa, karu, ongra.

Scholars consider ravishes to be a relatively new word group. Most of the idioms are the inflexible forms of nouns and verbs. The formal invariance of ravishes is its important morphological feature. Nouns have become inflected in some cases. In the case of verbs, there is a transition of the adverbs to the adverb. There are idioms in the ancient Turkic language that are absent in the modern Uzbek literary language. For example, o'tru (then), kiswa (after), karu (back), ongra (forward, in front of), etc. Some rituals have changed in form and content. For example, ancient bag (whole), now in the form of khop, and the meaning is also slightly narrowed. It now has the form of amti.

In the Old Turkic language, the adverbial suffixes are:

1. Suffix - d, - t, - ti:

qatg' (hard) - qatshdi (hard) adgu (good) - adguti (better)

2. - la, - la suffix: tun (night) - tunla (at night) ch y n (chin) - chnla

(really)

3. -cha, -cha suffix:

Azrak (very little) - Azrakchi (very little), Turkish (Turk) - Turkish (to Turk) 4. - pa, - pa suffix: as (ost) - asra (under), ich (ich) - ichra (inside) The use of these additions, as well as the above, depends on the thickness and thinness of the base, whether it is lipped or not. This suffix is formed from -garu, -garu. Apart from that, in the Turkish language, as in the modern Turkic languages, tense and space and instrumental agreement adverbs can also form a verb.

In the old Uzbek language, the ravish category is characterized by the fact that it does not accept word-changing affixes. This case is a distinctive feature of the ravish group from other independent word groups. In a sentence, adverbs are connected with other words by conjunctions. The agreement affixes in the composition of various idioms have lost their grammatical character and become part of the word. A certain part of idioms used in the old Uzbek language and words used in the meaning of idioms were borrowed from languages of

other systems. Most of these words belong to the Iranian language, and some to the Arabic language: Āhista aytduq y m y zn y ham şyt ü r (Tafsir). I don't like anything (Kissasi Rabguzi). Uchr ə di nāgāh opponent (Lutfiy). Dāimā mastu bekhabar k ö r ü n ü r (A toiy).

The main part of the idioms in use in the old Uzbek language consists of artificial words, which were formed by morphological and syntactic methods. There are very few native Uzbek dialects. Among them , the following can be shown : Our ancestors died (Tafsir). Bat bol, bash yñ al, kach (A toiy). In the old Uzbek language, some idioms, which were considered as root words, were actually artificial idioms. For example, the words naru (nari), beru (beri) were formed by adding the old transitive suffix -ru to the words na meaning distance and be meaning closeness. In the old Uzbek language, adverbs are formed from various word groups with the following affixes: adverbs made with the affix -cha/-ch ə express the meaning of the state, quantity, level of an action or indicate the similarity of one action sign to another action sign. . This affix is added to various words to form a verb:

is added to the noun: A 's also say Turkish (Navoi "Muhokamat ul lugatayn").

2. It is added to personal and demonstrative pronouns: Dunyāda bar-mu ek ə n mench ə yaman ("Shaybaniynama"). No one will give you anything , ayyar, kash-u köz (Lutfiy).

3. It is added to the adjective: Pādshāhzādarn gave the great great and the small ə small ə (Shajarayi tarokima). The affix -гача/-г э ч ə / -гача/-к э ч ə is a compound affix formed by adding the affix -cha/-ч ə to the case of dispatch , noun, adjective , pronoun, form ravish from words in the ravish family:

T ü ng ə ch ə to hit k ö ksig ə tash (Navoi). Until this week, the news was liked (Shayboniynoma), the affix -tek/-dek forms a adverb expressing the meaning of simile, comparison: Sakkākiy kö z yash y n yaz yamgur y -tek yag'durur (Sakkokiy). Kö rm ə g ə n bir sen-dke ahli rozg'ar (Navoi).

-la/-l ə is added to nouns with the meaning of time, mainly to the words ta ñ , tun, to form a time form: T ü nl ə -aq etty oshul kargan'a (Shaybaniynoma). Emdi ta ñ la bu s öz A bid khan'a yet ə r (Shajarayi Turk). The affix -āna is added to a noun to form a simile. This form was adopted into the Uzbek language from Iranian languages: Seni men ö lt ü r ü r-men, teb aytt y turkāna (Sakkoki). Hayley was a brave young man (Boburnoma). The affix -an was rarely used in the old Uzbek language: Ulug'l y g' y approximately on qar y bol'gay (Boburnoma).

There is almost no difference between the old Uzbek language and the modern Uzbek language in terms of the syntactical method of making a sentence.

Compound adverbs are formed with the following words:

1. By adding time, place, and similar words to one word: Be patient without you for a moment (Lutfiy). Please settle me somewhere . _ _ (Boburnoma).

2. By adding words indicating time or place to each demonstrative pronoun: Har kun salamga barur erdim (Tafsir). Wherever you go , you will be in slavery ("Boburnoma") .

3. By adding words indicating time or place to pronouns such as ul, bu, oshal: K özü l ü m ul yān tartadur (Lutfiy). It was a great fall (Boburnoma).

4. By adding words indicating time or space to the pronouns Hech, Kay: Hech zamanda no kikum khishtk ə nv ə k ö rg ə n yaktur (Shajarayi tarokima).

Old Uzbek idioms can also be semantically classified as follows:

1. Case adverbs: āhista, ravān, āsān, āgāh, tū rkch ə , āsh y qāna.

2. Time adverbs: t ü nl ə , hargiz, nāgāh, always, damādam, dam-badam, every time, every moment, first, hālā.

3. Adverbs of place: har sar y , here, in this, anda.

4. Degree-quantity expressions: az, k ö p, b ü rg ü tch ə , mench ə , ulugcha, ghayat, baghayat.

5. Border idioms: haftagacha, k ö kk ə ch ə , Ghazn y ghacha, akhshāmgacha, especially batakhsis.

6. Similes: lala-dek, nose-like, nangu-dek, yeg ü tek, paritek.

In the Uzbek language of the 19th century, more and more idioms were actively used compared to previous periods. They are divided into two types based on their origin;

1. Original Uzbek idioms: many, little, otu, asru, okush, art y da, kal y n, inside, outside y , yukar y , before, nose, after, y y raq, yak y n, as in all y , as in ald y .

2. idioms adopted from other languages.

a) idioms adopted from the Arabic language: mainly, roughly, filhal, alhal, abas, muntazir, absolutely, minbad, ittifaga, of course.

b) idioms that have been adopted from the Persian-Tajik language: □□□□□, pinkhana, yakbara, tabara, zinhor, ahista, payvasta, hargiz, nagah, hala, hazir, bistar, andak, ghayat, baz, hila, az tazi dil, mardanavar, like sherona.

According to their morphological structure, ravishes have a simple, joint, double character. Adverbs have simple, comparative and accretive degrees, and

from the semantic point of view, they consist of adverbs of case, quantity, degree, place and time.

In the morphological structure of the 19th century, adjectives were used in simple, artificial, compound and double forms. In the 19th century, the transfer of words from one word group to another word group is typical, and this behavior is also typical for the word group. Such migration is also typical for adverbialization (adverbialization).

In modern Uzbek, the word *birpas* is used as an adverb. The first part of this word is *number*, and the second element is *pas*. This word is not currently used. However, in the 19th century, *pas ravishi* was actively used. In this period, adjectives also had three types of simple, comparative and accusative degrees. In the 19th century, idioms in Uzbek were divided into the following semantic types:

1. Mood: softly, bravely, on foot, on foot, a little bit, quietly, quietly, slowly, quietly, hob, secretly, seriously.

2. Case adverbs with a sense of analogy: These are mostly made with the help of affixes such as *-ona*, *-dek*, *-cha*, *-vor*.

3. Adverbs indicating that the action was sudden:
Dafatan, suddenly (suddenly, suddenly), *nagah*, *banagah*, *ittiftraaqa*, *chust*, *dast*, *bot*, *zud*, immediately, *filhal*, *alhal*, *ildam*, *tez*.

4. Adverbs that indicate the reason for the performance of the action:
neilaj, *lailaj*, *zaruratdin*, *necessaritane*.

5. Adverbs that mean the repeated performance of an action: again, again, again, again, repeatedly.

6. Expressions that express the mental state of a person: *sad*, *sad*, *involuntary*, *happy*, *sadan*.

7. Idioms indicating how the speech is expressed: in my opinion, as far as I know, in Russian, as if.

Quantity-level development:

Quantitative adverbs refer to how much and to what extent an action is performed. They are divided into two types:

a) action, sometimes adverbs showing the redundancy and strength of the object sign: many, *ziyada*, *bisyar*, *artuksi*, *abadan*, *asru*, *ghayat*, *nihayat*, *nihayasiz*, *bagayat*, *benihayat*, *base*, like *tamoman*, *tola*, *trick*, *tabara*.

In the 19th century, most of the level approaches were not actively used. On the other hand, some pairs of nouns are used as adverbs of quantity and degree, such as *alamalam*, *group-group*, *tob-tob*.

b) behaviors that compare and contrast the amount of an action or object. These are formed by adding the affix -cha to nouns and pronouns. For example, kiyamatcha, I think, ulcha, much, so much.

The meaning of place is divided into three groups:

1. Verbs denoting place; ost, ust, uza, tashra, tashkar y , inside, kosh y da , all y da, aldida, argada, atra, aridisa, anda, munda, and y n, as in this.

Some of the adverbs with the sense of place are formed with the help of the affix: like son y ncha, at y ncha, yolcha.

2. Adverbs meaning distance: far, y y raq, yaq y n

3. Adverbs expressing the meaning of side: mind, left, right, left, attru, then, right, before, up, plane , ataq, all y , ald y nda, arqas y da, ul yan, bu yan , like yaq, tegra.

Period: In the 19th century, period was very productive in terms of its application. They are three types in terms of meaning;

1. Adverbs that mean the general moment;

a) avisdhs expressing the meaning of the previous time: first, first, nose, exion, like old age.

b) adverbs expressing the meaning of the present tense: like hala, hanuz, alhal.

Alhal, the words of Alwaqt are Arabic, and now, at this time, they mean their meanings. In the 19th century, the word Hala was used in meanings such as now, for the time being, this time. This word was later used in colloquial speech in its form due to changes in form and meaning. In the modern Uzbek literary language, this word is used only in the form of yet, and it expresses the meanings of the three tenses, such as a little earlier, at the moment, and a little later.

Words such as badaz, an, ahirul amr, minbad, and aknun, which were used in the 19th century, later fell out of use.

c) adverbs expressing the meaning of constant time: always, always, every time, every time as always.

g) action, which means that an event sometimes happens idioms: sometimes, like gaha, gah-gah.

d) that the action, event happened recently, suddenly Meaningful adverbs: again, now, suddenly, suddenly.

Adverbs representing the days of the week: today, tomorrow, the next day, tangla, taklas y , tuna kun.

3. Words representing different times of the day:

a) ravishes meaning the time of the morning; early morning at dawn, like alsabah.

b) adverbs denoting the time of day kundsz, chashtgah, noon such as.

c) idioms that express the meaning of night and evening: namaz zigar, asir, namaz, sham, kach, kach, kach, kacherat, shabana, etc.

In the Uzbek language of the 19th century, the quantity and level of use of ravishes was quite wide, there were more than a hundred of them, and artificial ravishes were widely used.

During this period, it is common to make ravish by the method of affixation and composition. In addition, there are many borrowed idioms in the Uzbek language. As shown above, some ravishes have undergone phonetic changes.

References:

1. Abdullaev A. Morphological method of meaning enhancement // Uzbek language and literature, 1970, issue 1. - B. 24-27.
2. Asadov T.A. About the Ravish vocabulary and its composition // Uzbek language and literature, 2005, issue 2. - B. 53-55.
3. Asadov T. _ Word categories in the system ravish : Philol . science _ name _ ... dis . autoref . - Tashkent , 2009. -23 p .
4. Alamova M. Semantic-stylistic characteristics of accretive forms // Collection of scientific works of ToshDU, No. 648. - Tashkent, 1980. - B. 61-65.
5. Bozorov O. Grading in Uzbek: Philology. science. doctor... dis. afterref. - Tashkent, 1997.

